

Synthesis of Contaminants and Degradation Products of Anilofos[#]

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Anilofos [*S*-(*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-isopropylcarbamoylmethyl)-*O,O*-dimethyldithiophosphate; 1] is a preemergence herbicide¹ recommended for the control of grassy as well as broad leaf weeds in rice. Contaminants in pesticides may be more hazardous than the parent compound and may lead to environmental pollution. The impurities are either introduced at the time of manufacture or develop as a result of chemical transformation on storage of the technical or formulated product. Hence, these products are often tested for the active ingredients and the impurities of the pesticides. For the identification of impurities in anilofos six contaminants have been synthesised. Here we report our results.

- (1) R = S
(8) R = O

- (3) R = H
(4) R = COCH₂Cl
(6) R = COCH₂SH
(7) R = COCH₂SCH₃
(9) R = COCH₃

- (2) R = H
(5) R = COCH₂Cl
(10) R = COCH₃

Results and Discussion

p-Chlorophenylamine (2) on reaction with isopropyl bromide in benzene in the presence of triethyl amine gave 3. From a doublet at δ 1.23 (*J* 7 Hz) for six protons and a quintet at δ 3.55 (*J* 7 Hz) in the ¹H nmr spectrum for an isopropyl unit 3 was assigned the structure as *p*-chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl amine. Compound 3 was also synthesised by reacting 2 with isopropylbromide in acetone in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

Compound 4 was obtained by the reaction of 3 with

chloroacetyl chloride in benzene in the presence of triethyl amine. ¹H nmr spectrum of 4, besides other usual signals, showed a singlet for two protons at δ 3.80 showing the presence of an α -chloroacetyl group and has characterised as *p*-chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl- α -chloroacetamide. Similarly, *p*-chlorophenyl- α -chloroacetamide (5) was prepared by the reaction of 2 with chloroacetyl chloride.

Compounds 2-5 are the suspected contaminants introduced from the intermediate stages in the process of synthesis of anilofos. Since hydrolysis and oxidation of anilofos on storage can also cause contamination of the sample, such reactions of anilofos were also carried out. On hydrolysis with aqueous sodium hydroxide in methanol 1 gave 7 as the major product, and not the expected *p*-chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl- α -mercaptoacetamide (6). Besides usual signals of an isopropyl group, a carbamoylmethyl group and aromatic protons, the ¹H nmr of 7 showed a singlet for three protons appearing at δ 2.14, which could be attributed to a methyl group. Compound 7 gave a positive sodium nitroprusside test for elemental sulphur. These observations were consistent with the structure of 7 as *p*-chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl- α -mercaptomethylacetamide. The mass spectral data also supported the structural assignment. Oxidation of anilofos with potassium permanganate in acidic medium gave the major product 8. ¹H nmr and mass spectral data supported the structure of 8 as *S*-(*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-isopropylcarbamoylmethyl)-*O,O*-dimethyl thiophosphate.

Compound 9 and 10 were obtained after acetylating 3 and 2 respectively, with acetic anhydride-pyridine.

All the synthesised compounds responded well in hplc using uv-detector. The *R*_f values of the compounds can be used for comparison purposes for detecting the

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impurities in anilofos. Besides, compounds **2**, **3**, **7–10** can also serve as the metabolic products of anilofos in soil, plant, animals and microbial systems. The oxon type of compounds such as **8** are well known products in the metabolism of phosphorodithioates². Similarly, *N*-acetyl derivatives such as **9** and **10** are also well known metabolic products of substituted anilines in pure microbial cultures³. Hence these synthesised compounds can also be used as authentic samples in various metabolic studies of anilofos for their identification.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on Varian EM-360 spectrometer (60 MHz) and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 instrument. Purity and mobility of compounds were checked by reverse phase hplc using Spectra Physics-8000 B, RP-18 column with MeOH–H₂O (4 : 1) as the mobile phase and uv-detector at 254 nm. Anilofos (technical; 90%) was provided by M/s. Gharda Chemicals Ltd., India. All the compounds gave satisfactory carbon and hydrogen analysis.

p-Chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropylamine (**3**). *Method A* : To a solution of *p*-chlorophenylamine (**2**; 1 g, 7.8 mmol) and isopropyl bromide (0.8 ml, 8.4 mmol) in benzene (30 ml), Et₃N (6–7 drops) was added and the mixture was gently heated for 4–5 h equipped with cold water-condenser. Solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and water was added to the residue. The suspension was extracted with ether, ethereal layer dried (Na₂SO₄), distilled and the residue was purified by column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of column with hexane gave **3** as light brown oil (0.8 g, 60%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.23 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C(CH₃)₂), 3.30 (1H, bd merged with m, exchangeable with D₂O, NH), 3.55 (1H, quintet merged with d, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 6.42 and 7.10 (each 2H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH); hplc *R*_t, 186 s.

Method B : To a solution of **2** (1 g, 7.8 mmol) and isopropyl bromide (0.8 ml, 8.4 mmol) in acetone (30 ml), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3 g) was added and the mixture was gently heated on a water bath for 7–8 h. Working up gave **3** as brown oil (0.7 g, 53%).

p-Chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl- α -chloroacetamide (**4**). To a solution of **3** (0.2 g, 1.17 mmol) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.1 ml, 1.25 mmol) in benzene (20 ml), Et₃N

(3–4 drops) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. Working up gave a solid, which was crystallised from benzene-hexane as colourless needles (0.26 g, 90%), m.p. 66–67°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C(CH₃)₂), 3.80 (2H, s, COCH₂Cl), 5.12 (1H, quintet, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 7.35 and 7.75 (each 2H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH); hplc, *R*_t 246 s.

p-Chlorophenyl- α -chloroacetamide (**5**) : A solution of **2** (0.2 g, 1.57 mmol), chloroacetyl chloride (0.13 ml, 1.62 mmol) and Et₃N (3–4 drops) in benzene (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. Working up as in case of **4** gave a solid which was crystallised from ethyl alcohol as colourless needles (0.17 g, 83%), m.p. 168–69°. δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.90 (2H, s, COCH₂Cl), 6.90 and 7.28 (each 2H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH); hplc, *R*_t 252 s.

p-Chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropyl- α -mercaptomethylacetamide (**7**) : To a solution of anilofos (0.5 g, 1.39 mmol) in methanol (10 ml) was added aqueous 1 *N* NaOH (3.5 ml) and the mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 6–7 h. The solvent was then removed and the residue diluted with water, extracted with ether followed by ethyl acetate, dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to dryness. The dark coloured residue thus obtained was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. The major fraction was eluted with benzene which on evaporation gave **7** as light brown oil (0.12 g, 34%). δ (CDCl₃) 1.08 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C(CH₃)₂), 2.14 (3H, s, S-CH₃), 2.65 (2H, s, COCH₂-S-), 4.80 (1H, quintet, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 7.05 and 7.35 (each 2H, d, *J* 9.5 Hz, ArH); MS (rel.int.) *m/z* 257 (59.1%, *M*⁺), 242 (2.1%, *M*⁺-CH₃), 210 (98.9%, *M*⁺-SCH₃), 168 (95.7%, *M*⁺-C₃H₅OS), 153 (98.9%, *M*⁺-C₄H₈OS); hplc, *R*_t 354 s.

S-*N*-(4-Chlorophenyl)-*N*-isopropyl carbamoylmethyl-O,O dimethylthiophosphate (**8**) : To a stirred solution of anilofos (0.5 g, 1.39 mmol) in glacial CH₃COOH (5 ml), a solution of KMnO₄ (1 g, 6.3 mmol) in water (12 ml) was added dropwise within a period of 1 h. The mixture was stirred for 15–20 h, then diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate (3×50 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), distilled and the residue, thus obtained, was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene gave **8** as brown oil (0.15 g, 31.2%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.00 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C(CH₃)₂), 3.10 (2H, d, *J* 17 Hz, COCH₂-S-P-), 3.45 (6H, d, *J* 17 Hz, 2×OCH₃), 4.70 (1H, quintet, *J* 7 Hz, CH), 6.75 and 7.05 (each 2H, d,

J 9.5 Hz, ArH); MS (rel. int.) m/z 351 (10%, M^+), 210 (60%, $M^+ - C_2H_6O_3PS$); hplc, R_t 203 s.

N-Acetyl-*p*-chlorophenyl-*N*-isopropylamine (9): To a solution of 3 (0.1 g, 0.58 mmol) in acetic anhydride (2 ml), pyridine (2 drops) was added. The solution was kept at room temperature for 24 h, then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (0.11 g, 88%), m.p. 86–87°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.05 (6H, d, J 7 Hz, C(CH₃)₂), 1.75 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.95 (1H, quintet, J 7 Hz, CH), 7.00 and 7.37 (each 2H, d, J 9.5 Hz, ArH); hplc, R_t 232 s.

N-Acetyl-*p*-chlorophenylamine (10) · Acetylation of 2 (0.1 g, 1.56 mmol) with acetic anhydride and pyridine at room temperature gave 10 (0.1 g, 76%) which was crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 177–78° (lit⁴. m.p. 178.4°); hplc, R_t 243 s.

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